

Developing a New Customer Journey Path: Case Study on a Fixed Broadband ISP Company

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ABSTRACT: The need for internet connectivity use has grown to the point that it can be considered a primary need that cannot be separated from the support of many needs and sectors of life. This momentum has attracted InterHome as one of the providers of fixed broadband Internet Service Providers (ISP) to meet these needs. As a result, the value of the engagement rate, which increased significantly in 2021 compared to the previous year but this thing is inversely proportional to the InterHome brand's sentiment, which fluctuated every month in 2021 and, on average, rarely reached the point where the brand sentiment became an illustration of the context behind the interaction. In this study, using external and internal analysis in the analysis of the business environment, it is obtained an overview of the significant competitive industry contained in the SWOT analysis. As a follow-up to the problems faced by InterHome, the author proposes a customer journey using the 5 A's Customer Journey Path guidelines from Marketing 5.0 by Philip Kotler, Hermawan Kartajaya, and Iwan Setiawan to obtain a portrait of the existing and expected conditions by InterHome customers. While the company has made various attempts to date, there is still a lack of investigation into what customers need and desire on each journey. Therefore, this study aims to increase customer retention in line with increasing positive brand sentiments and reach the target using a customer journey approach. The combination of quantitative and qualitative is used in this study, where quantitative data brings a breadth of research, and qualitative data allows depth. As a result of the study, the proposed customer journey can be described at the 5 A's stages, providing a clear view of the improvement initiatives that could be a solution for each stage and helping companies align around common goals. The detailed mapping of the proposed customer journey is divided into six key points, including common customer activities that explain what InterHome consumers typically do when they decide to subscribe to InterHome. Furthermore, customer needs and desires represent what customers will seek to be captured by the brand at every stage of its journey. The point where the consumer interacts with the brand is described as the touchpoint in the customer journey. Business goals and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are measurable values that will measure the company's performance and success in achieving business goals and in line with the implementation of data-based marketing.

KEYWORDS: Fixed Broadband, Internet Service Provider, Business Environment Analysis, Customer Journey Path

1. INTRODUCTION

The human desire for the internet has grown with the passage of time. The internet's early development, which was limited, has now evolved into a core human need that cannot be separated, and its users have become diverse globally. The internet is an interconnected network, which is defined as an extensive computer network that connects millions of computers [1]. The internet facilitates human needs and lives by speeding up forms of connection, linking people and content, providing access to various information, and supporting economic development. According to Badan Pusat Statistik [2], household internet usage penetration in Indonesia during 2020 increased by 4.4 points to 78.2% compared to the previous year, as shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Penetration Household Internet Usage (2016 - 2020) [2]

This is in line with the growing need for fixed broadband ISP to fulfil the evolving needs of people's behaviour as they begin to transition to an all-online and digital. InterHome, as one of the players in the fixed broadband ISP industry in Indonesia, plays an essential role in meeting the internet needs of the community through the development of products, services and technology to meet customer aspirations and needs by providing the best consumer experience use a customer journey approach. InterHome is encouraged to provide excellent service to all its customers, starting with providing the best connectivity to fast and responsive services related to handling disturbances. InterHome has optimised various social media to increase public awareness and engagement with its audience through multiple types of content. The successful performance of InterHome's content marketing performance, as reflected in the value of the engagement rate in 2021 increased significantly compared to 2020. This result indicates that content performance on various InterHome social media platforms has successfully engaged the audience with published posts. Simultaneously, public knowledge of the InterHome brand will automatically increase. However, the results of calculating the engagement rate value as quantitative data are not enough to be an indicator that a brand can be said to be able to fulfil customer desires, brand sentiment analysis can be used to go further by analysing the context behind the interaction to get deeper insights. Brand sentiment refers to the underlying emotions expressed in brand mentions by extracting, changing, and interpreting opinions from a text and classifying them into positive, negative, or neutral sentiments [3]. Confirmed in an in-depth interview with InterHome's Head of Marketing, it is known that the increase in engagement rate in 2021 is inversely proportional to the achievement of brand sentiment value in the last one throughout 2021, which fluctuates every month and, on average, barely never reaching the target as shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. InterHome Brand Sentiment 2021 [4]

This occurrence was caused by several disruption issues related to InterHome products and services that were complained about by customers who shared their unpleasant experiences through various communication channels by explicitly mentioning the InterHome, thereby increasing the potential for provocation of other InterHome customers. The expression of customers' thoughts and feelings through brand sentiment analysis is important for companies to monitor and understand customer feedback and critical issues. Reviews and conversations on communication channels allow companies to learn what makes customers happy or frustrated so that they can be used to tailor products or services that can meet customer needs at every stage of the customer journey. This study aims to develop a suitable strategy to enhance InterHome customer retention through a positive customer journey to maintain customer trust to continue to be loyal to InterHome and prevent them from switching to competitors.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis combines external and internal analysis to create a complete picture of how the company functions as an individual entity and part of a more significant competitive industry by maximizing strengths, improving weaknesses, taking advantage of opportunities, and overcoming the possible threats [5]. An external and internal analysis in this study was carried out using a generic framework divided into two types which are external using Porter's 5 Forces to analyse how the competitive environment in the fixed broadband ISP industry will affect the marketing of InterHome products. In contrast, the internal analysis uses STP and 7Ps Marketing Mix to assist market analysis and determine the marketing strategies of InterHome. Wherein both of which data collection uses primary data in the form of in-depth interviews and secondary data.

2.2. Customer Journey Path

The habit of the consumer journey process from initially deciding independently has changed to deciding together with his community, friends, and family through sharing opinions and reviews related to various products and services on the market [6]. The concept of the customer journey has also been adjusted, which initially only consisted of 4 A's to 5 A's Customer Journey Path [7]. The customer journey maps the relationship of a company's brand with its consumers, which allows the stages of customer behaviour

towards a brand starting with everyone knowing the brand’s existence, so they want to buy and finally recommend the brand to others. The 5 A's Customer Journey Path consists of Aware, Appeal, Ask, Act, and Advocate. In this study, through the InterHome customer journey questionnaire using The 5 A's Customer Journey Path was used to measure each stage of the journey that the customer went through to help get a perspective on what customers wanted when they first got to know InterHome until they finally decided to subscribe and recommend InterHome products and services.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted using a mixed-method approach that combines quantitative and qualitative research [8]. Quantitative research relies on the methods of natural sciences, which produce numerical data and hard facts [9]. Therefore, a quantitative research method deals with quantifying and analyzing variables to get results in numerical form and explores a construct of graphs and tables to facilitate analysis [10]. The quantitative research method uses an online questionnaire based on a thematic framework for strategies exploration that aims to obtain a portrait of the existing and expected conditions of InterHome customers. On the other hand, qualitative research is a form of social action that stresses the way people interpret and make sense of their experiences in a humanistic, interpretive approach [11]. Qualitative research consists of unstructured techniques like interview analysis methods, participant observation, open interviews, in-depth interviews, and others [12]. This research used a qualitative method to gather, analyze, interpret, and present the data by conducting in-depth interviews with representatives from InterHome and observations to capture the company's business ecosystem, identify current marketing strategy, and current challenges faced by digital marketing operations InterHome. Moreover, quantitative data brings a breadth of research, and qualitative data allows depth.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Business Environmental Analysis

Business environmental analysis is used to determine external and internal factors that may negatively or positively impact the company's marketing strategy. The company will have a broader understanding of the environment's impact on its success by examining the analysis of the business environment. The goal of a company's strategy should be to obtain a long-term competitive edge. As a result, the external environment industry is the focus of the company's business unit strategy. The external environment encompasses factors and forces beyond the company's control and influences how it operates [13]. The external environmental analysis compensates for the SWOT analysis' opportunities and threats. Meanwhile, internal analysis is a comprehensive analysis of the company's tangible and intangible internal components. According to Sammut-Bonnici & Galae [14], internal analysis of a firm is crucial in finding sources of competitive advantage and establishing a feasible business plan. The company can discover its strengths and weaknesses through this analysis [15].

Table 1. InterHome SWOT Analysis

	Helpful Strengths (S):	Harmful Weaknesses (W):
Internal Origin	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. InterHome as one of the products and services of a State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs) engaged in the telecommunications sector has a strong public image and appeal, and it is suggestive because it is a well-known and valuable brand. 2. InterHome is constantly innovating to provide a diverse range of products and services. 3. InterHome coverage reaches the entire country of Indonesia. 4. InterHome offers the use of fiber optic technology, which has a number of benefits for customers. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. InterHome requires a lengthy and complex bureaucracy to make decisions about implementing marketing innovation ideas. 2. InterHome does not market its products and services to the low affordability segment, which has a population of almost 20 million people due to the long rate of return. 3. The management of a large number of human resources necessitates a focused and appropriate approach considering the possibility for high turnover in the field to occur easily.
External Origin	<p>Opportunities (O):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Massive digital acceleration of transformation due to changes in people's habits that have become entirely digital and online requires high internet access. 2. People's lifestyles are rapidly changing, requiring products and services to adapt and take advantage of the latest technological breakthroughs. 3. Government support in penetrating the fixed broadband ISP industry must be put to good use. 	<p>Threats (T):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Competition comes from various sources, including fellow State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs), private companies, foreign companies to local players. 2. Competitive allegations that lower prices raise over promise under deliver have sparked a violent pricing war in the fixed broadband ISP industry. 3. There are substitute products with a very significant level of functionality and similarity.

Strengths (S): InterHome maintained its position as the market leader in fixed broadband ISP in Indonesia, with a considerable rise in the number of subscribers, demonstrating InterHome's value as a well-known and valuable brand. The company's consolidated revenue increased as a result of this. InterHome offers a diverse range of products and services, including both basic and innovative add-on services, whereas most of its competitors only offer the most common products. The concept of one-stop shopping gives the impression that it is simple for customers to fulfil their needs in one brand in one visit, thereby attracting clients and reducing the complexity of discovering items and services that meet their needs. InterHome's products and services are available throughout Indonesia, with a reach of 496 regions covering from Sabang to Merauke. Fiber optics are used in InterHome products and services to provide a stable, fast, and reliable connection for the Indonesian people's needs.

Weaknesses (W): InterHome's consideration of the deployment and execution of marketing innovation ideas to disseminate information, influence, and persuade the target audience to create demand for its products or services necessitates a long and complex agreement based on company policies that are subject to the values of State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs), resulting in execution constraints. InterHome also does not market its products and services to the segment with the largest population of almost 20 million people or to the segment with the lowest affordability because of the segment's high rate of return. No less significant is human resources play a vital part in organizations' ability to supply products or services and impact client perceptions to make purchases, which necessitates better and continuous management because there are so many of them with different personalities to avoid excessive employee turnover.

Opportunities (O): Changes in people's behaviours as they become more digital and online in their daily lives necessitate high internet access, which is in accordance with company's commitment for digital transformation through InterHome, a firm that provides fixed broadband internet services. InterHome products and services must be more integrated due to changes in habits as well as the lifestyle of people who require the latest technology in every element of their lives to make their lives easier. Because the government is aware of the shift in behaviour, Indonesia's attempts to enhance fixed broadband penetration are increasingly encouraged to benefit the sector.

Threats (T): Competitors' threats are inescapable in any sector, including the fixed broadband ISP industry, where InterHome plays a role. Competition in the fixed broadband business today comes from various sources, including fellow State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs), private companies, foreign companies, and local players. InterHome must be able to quickly overcome this competition by selling its products and services aggressively. Excessive competition claims in the market, along with the low prices being given, are fueling a severe pricing war that could threaten the fixed broadband ISP industry's health. In addition to competitors, InterHome faces threats from substitute products with a high level of function and similarity and can easily give solutions to the society's internet connection needs, particularly in places where InterHome has not yet penetrated.

4.2. Proposed Strategy

On the proposed strategy, InterHome can accommodate all customer reviews and conversations to learn what makes customers happy by providing products or services that are in line with customer desires and needs, as well as providing improvements to frustrating points at each stage of the customer journey using the 5 A's Customer Journey Path guidelines from Marketing 5.0 by Philip Kotler, Hermawan Kartajaya, dan Iwan Setiawan. The author also considers customer preferences when subscribing to InterHome by considering the results of the need attributes of customer interest in six integrated digital media channels to build communication channels that support the customer journey to be more enjoyable, resulting in satisfaction and encouraging customer trust in InterHome, leads to increased customer retention and in line with increasing positive brand sentiments and can reach the target. **Table 2** maps the details of the customer journey solutions to present a clear view of the improvement initiatives that could be a solution for each stage of the customer journey and helps companies align around a common goal.

4.2.1. Proposed Aware Stage

In the aware stage, potential InterHome consumers are passive, which can be described as merely receiving brand messaging without actively learning and researching the products or services offered by a vast variety of fixed broadband ISP brands. At this stage, the company must be able to raise brand awareness by informing potential customers about the brand's existence and its relationship to the products offered, as well as the implications for potential customers' lives [16]. Brand awareness is created when potential customers recognize or remember a brand because it is in their memory, they can immediately mention the brand they recall [17]. According to Chaffey [18], brand awareness may be increased by boosting interactions across different search engine media touchpoints, which drive traffic to digital and social media advertising. The use of interaction at predetermined touchpoints is collaborated with marketing automation to be able to streamline and simplify the marketing and promotion process through various media automatically. A marketing automation system's installation begins with identifying audiences, matching appropriate content, and automating marketing based on schedules and consumer behaviour. This can be determined using a collection of data derived from a variety of interactions, such as historical cookie data and search engine and social media searches. Considering the repeated nature of marketing interactions, a marketing automation system can help enhance operational efficiency.

The use of relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) at the aware stage, such as unique visitors, number of clicks, and search engine traffic to advertisements, is used as a reference for companies to carry out marketing activities according to priorities and consider evaluations based on digital analytics to show which marketing activities are effective and which are not. It will also go through the innovative solutions for integrated digital media channels, digital advertisements, and social media advertisements that have taken customer preferences into consideration for various digital media channels in detail.

4.2.2. Proposed Appeal Stage

As part of the aware stage, potential customers will evaluate all of the messages they receive from the display and social media advertising in order to develop a memory and attract them to a specific brand, causing them to become interested in choosing one brand. At this stage of the appeal, potential buyers evaluate the brand message's relevance to their needs and desires, as well as the ability to obtain inspiration from the product or service offered in order to be genuinely motivated to submit a subscription. In this stage, the touchpoints that are optimized are digital media channels that can supply all of the information needed by customers to learn about the various products and services offered by InterHome and fit their needs and preferences. The number of new digital media channels visitors, which indicates the number of visitors in multiple digital media channels that will be suggested at this stage, is one of the important Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) used at the appeal stage.

At the appeal stage, the suggested digital marketing media channels effort combines the optimization of creative and synchronous content across all digital media. This is related to the actions taken in response to consumer feedback, which said that they desired relevant information and a match between the keywords they searched for on the search engine. As a result, at this point, further information on Search Engine Optimization (SEO), digital public relations, and landing page optimization will be addressed.

4.2.3. Proposed Ask Stage

Potential customers who have gone through the appeal stage will move on to the ask stage, where they will be driven by a strong desire to learn more about the brand, so they will actively investigate it to develop more confidence. At this point, potential customers typically seek additional information from friends, family, the media, or the brand directly to re-confirm the offer was made by the brand's product or service [7]. Most potential customers will conduct various investigations at this point to learn from the experiences of other customers who have made transactions to subscribe to InterHome products and services by reviews from digital media channels and social media through Electronic Word of Mouth (e-WOM) [19]. Furthermore, today's modern potential customers are influenced significantly to make subscription transactions by public figures, influencers, or Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs), who exert broad influence over potential customers by introducing a number of new messages or popularizing certain issues related to a brand's product or services.

In terms of meeting the needs of curiosity to gain deeper trust in the company, the company can optimize the provision of interactive customer service that is responsive to various customer questions by utilizing the knowledge base to answer basic customer questions and forwarding it to a live chat agent if the problem at hand has become too complex for bots to handle through Artificial Intelligence (AI) chatbots on the InterHome website and the MyInterHome mobile application. Not only optimizing on chat via chat but also Intelligent Interactive Voice Response (IVR) system can be used to fulfil customer support requests by routing calls to appropriate agents on demand. Both of these technologies enable businesses to provide potential consumers with real-time digital customer care. Engagement rates and leads, which measure potential customer interactions with the company's digital media channel management initiatives and the number of potential customers who eventually provide their personal data voluntarily to carry out subscription transactions at the next stage, are Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that are relevant in the ask stage.

4.2.4. Proposed Act Stage

Potential customers are turned into customers at this stage since they have made the confident decision to subscribe and interact more closely with their preferred brand [7]. Since InterHome uses multichannel or omnichannel marketing, the conversion step of subscribing to InterHome products and services on the act stage can be done via online or offline channels. Where subscriptions to pay for products or services are first offered online through the website, social media, and the MyInterHome mobile application to e-commerce, and offline through InterHome booths and Plasa InterHome.

Stage act optimization aims to increase sales and the conversion rate of consumer visits to digital media channels that result in subscription transactions. As a result, the organization must ensure that the stage act can provide customers with an effortless subscription experience and a pleasant after-interaction that will boost customer satisfaction. The organization can use the ideas to optimize digital media commerce and create interactive content on social media to ensure that the relationship between customers who have decided to subscribe to InterHome is well-established and long-lasting. The number of sales and the conversation rate are key performance indicators (KPIs) at this stage, and they serve as a reference for organizations in optimizing the digital buy funnel and content interaction.

4.2.5. Proposed Advocate Stage

Lastly, after a customer buys a product or service, it accommodates behaviours such as deeper connection through consumption and use of post-subscribed products and services at the advocate stage [7]. Customer loyalty is established at this stage, and the desire to share their experience of using a brand's product or service with others rises. Customers' positive advocacy can be obtained by delivering a satisfactory after-sales service support experience in order to keep loyal customers [20]. At this stage, the company may optimize its entire operation by organizing and automating customer service and managing consumer feedback to turn it into insights for establishing new companies. Customer happiness, organic conversion of customers into enthusiastic supporters, and increased customer retention are all benefits of business optimization. This is shown in the use of positive Net Promoter Score (NPS) and brand sentiment as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) on the advocacy stage. The suggested digital marketing media channels effort at the advocate stage includes optimizing interactive customer service through Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Intelligent Interactive Voice Response (IVR) systems which have been explained in detail on the ask stage and generating affiliate marketing in the form of a referral marketing with a mutual recognition system that attracts customers' attention so that they can share and attract other potential customers to make InterHome subscription transactions.

5. CONCLUSION

Given that brand sentiment throughout 2021 InterHome is experiencing a fluctuating and, on average, barely never reaching the target, the company is expected to monitor and understand customer feedback and the critical issues it faces, which are reflected in the value of the brand sentiment through positive customer journeys, to increase customer retention and maintain customer trust, preventing them from switching to competitors. By using SWOT analysis the company gets an overview of the combination of external and internal analysis that can be used as a guide for a significant competitive industry description by maximizing strengths, improving weaknesses, taking advantage of opportunities, and overcoming the possible threats. Meanwhile, to enhance InterHome customer retention, the author proposes a positive customer journey that can accommodate all customer reviews and conversations. The author then uses the 5 A's Customer Journey Path guidelines to accommodate customer activities as a guideline at each stage of the customer journey in order to provide products and services that are needed according to what customers want and need by optimizing touchpoints to be in line with company goals whose implementation performance can later be assessed in a measurable value or Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

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Table 2. Proposed InterHome Customer Journey

	AWARE	APPEAL	ASK	ACT	ADVOCATE
Customers Activities	Customers are passively exposed to promo ads and information about a long list of fixed broadband brands	Customers are looking for a certain brand among the many available fixed broadband brands	Customers seek further information on how to subscribe to the products and services offered by the fixed broadband brands they're interested in	Customers decide to subscribe and interact more deeply with the brand they choose	Customers develop a strong loyalty to the brand and begin to influence others
Customers' Needs and Desires	Understanding the implications of internet services in everyday life	1. Precisely matching brand messages with their needs and desires 2. Get inspired by the products or services before opting to subscribe	More convinced about the most in-demand internet service solutions	Subscription effortlessly and do enjoyable interaction with brands	Get a satisfying support experience and influence others about it
Touchpoints	Search engine and media social	Digital media channels	e-WOM, social media, mobile apps, and call center	Website, social media, mobile apps, e-commerce, and brick and mortar store	e-WOM, WOM, social media, mobile apps, and forums
Business Goals	Increase awareness and information of InterHome potential customers	Increase new digital media channels visitors	Increase engagement rate and leads acquired	Increase sales and conversation rate	Raise customer satisfaction and convert customers into enthusiastic supporters
KPI's	Unique visitors, the number of clicks, and search engine traffic	The number of new digital media channels visitors	Engagement rate and leads	The number of sales and conversation rate	Positive Net Promoter Score (NPS) and positive brand sentiment
Initiative Integrated Digital Media Channels	Continuous and automated digital marketing campaign 1.) Display Advertising 2.) Social Media Advertising	Creative and synchronous marketing content 1.) SEO 2.) Digital Public Relations 3.) Landing Page Optimization	Persuasive and integrated digital media channels, real-time digital support 1.) e-WOM and Micro and Nano Influencers 2.) Interactive Customer Service: AI Chatbot and Interactive Voice Response	Optimization of the digital purchase funnel and content interaction 1.) Digital Media Commerce Optimization 2.) Vertical Short Videos and Co-branding	Organize and automate customer service and management feedback, provide affiliate marketing 1.) Interactive Customer Service: AI Chatbot and Interactive Voice Response 2.) Referral Marketing

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